

The Effect of the War in Ukraine on the Footballers' Contracts

By: Prof. Ammar Alrefaei. Dean of the College of Business, Professor of Law, King Abdulaziz University Saudi Arabia.

The Annex number 7 of the Regulations on the Status and Transfer of Players (RSTP) entitled “Temporary rules addressing the exceptional situation deriving from the war in Ukraine” (Annex 7) is a special rule added to FIFA's Regulations on the Status and Transfer of Players. The Annex adopted after Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, suspended the contracts of foreign players and coaches in all Ukrainian football clubs. The Annex proposed to protect the players, but was created and delivered without prior consulting with the Ukrainian Association of Football or its clubs.

This paper reviews Annex 7 and how it was applied with the existing regulations and laws, taking in considering important sports objectives as sports competitiveness, and contractual stability. The paper concludes that with Annex 7, FIFA failed to effectively recognize the needs of UAF-affiliated clubs and take appropriate actions to address them. With the apparent issues concerning anti-competitive and discriminatory nature of Annex 7, there have been better alternatives that could satisfy both the players on the transfer and the clubs. Still, should FIFA maintain its hardline position and avoid serious legal consequences of its actions, there is a dangerous precedent of sport governing bodies’ possible abuse of power.

On February 24, 2022 Russia invaded Ukraine which brought much turmoil to the state of affairs in Europe and had far reaching consequences on a global scale. This act of aggression has received almost universal condemnation at both national and organizational levels. The major international sports governing bodies reacted with unprecedented resolve by stripping Russia and its ally Belarus the rights to host sports events and restricting participation for their national teams, clubs, and individual athletes¹. Along with these actions, sports organizations made it clear that the measures taken were in solidarity with Ukraine and were seen as one of the ways to end the conflict.

The Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) was not consistent in this regard. On February 27, 2022, it announced that both Russian and Belarusian national football teams and clubs would be allowed to continue participation in international competitions, although without home games and under neutral flags. However, after a boycott threat from the opponents of the Russian national team in the upcoming matches, FIFA changed its stance, banning Russia and its clubs from international matches and leagues altogether. UEFA followed the suit by removing Russian clubs from the Europa League and also ending all sponsorship contracts with Russian businesses. Yet, the most controversial regulation was issued in the beginning

¹ J Lindholm, ‘How Russia’s invasion of Ukraine shook sports’ foundation’ (2022) 22 The International Sports Law Journal 1-4.

of March under the title “Temporary rules addressing the exceptional situation deriving from the war in Ukraine”². In effect, the Rules allowed for a free release of football players and coaches from both Russian and Ukrainian leagues.

In a series of lawsuits that followed, the Ukrainian side represented by FC Shakhtar Donetsk attempted to challenge the Annex 7 amendments as unlawful. However, the Court of Arbitration for Sports (CAS) has rejected all those claims³. In a media release following the decision, the CAS Panel stated that the suspension of contracts was a result of “a legitimate objective” and within the powers granted to FIFA by law⁴. The CAS decision paints a mixed picture. On the one hand, FIFA’s decision may be interpreted as a desire to offer players and coaches an opportunity to legally escape the zone of the military conflict. On the other hand, Annex 7 clearly omitted the interests of the Ukrainian clubs by offering no support or compensation for the players’ exodus. This is especially surprising given the statement supplementing the amendments to Annex 7 where FIFA reiterated its “condemnation of the ongoing use of force by Russia in Ukraine”⁵.

This paper critically evaluates the new FIFA rules concerning players’ transfers in the wake of the conflict in Ukraine. The legal basis for the FIFA’s decision is examined through the lens of the FIFA statutes, regulations of transfers, and applicable laws. It argues that FIFA, as an umbrella organization of international football, has not been fair and balanced in its dealings with players and clubs on the matter. Specifically, there is a clear indication that FIFA has not been ready to consider the interests of the Ukrainian clubs, which may create a serious precedent for the future. As the legal battle over Annex 7 continues, such implications are discussed from the perspective of football clubs and sports law in general.

The war in Ukraine has seriously altered the European football landscape and challenged not only the way that many competitions are held but also the very principles upon the governance of the game stands. The decisions made by FIFA has been puzzling in this regard. While openly condemning the Russian invasion of Ukraine, it has implemented some decisions that not only failed to help the UAF-affiliated clubs but also hurt them in a number of ways. Annex 7 to RSTP 2022 can be hardly considered a supporting regulation. Understandably, it aimed to protect the players affiliated with the Ukrainian clubs by providing opportunities to escape the war and continue playing. However, this was done solely at the expense of the clubs with no due support or redeeming measures provided for the latter. In this way, Annex 7 failed to provide equal protection for the players and clubs.

² The rules are known as Annex 7 to the Regulations on The Status and Transfer of Players (RSTP) 2022. Hereafter, it is referred to as Annex 7.

³ CAS Media Release: Football Regulatory (FIFA RSTP), January 13, 2023, p. 1. Retrieved from https://www.tas-cas.org/fileadmin/user_upload/CAS_Media_Release_9016_9017.pdf

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ ‘Media Release: FIFA adopts temporary employment and registration rules to address several issues in relation to war in Ukraine’, March 7, 2022. Retrieved from <https://www.fifa.com/about-fifa/organisation/fifa-council/media-releases/fifa-adopts-temporary-employment-and-registration-rules-to-address-several>

It was demonstrated in this paper that Annex 7 has somewhat questionable legal foundations and that it may, in fact, contradict the existing regulations, including those prescribed by the European Union's and Swiss law. However, the complexity and scope of the legal challenges surrounding Annex 7 is probably wider. As the case goes to the Swiss Supreme Court, some difficult questions remain. First, to what extent can FIFA's decisions like contract suspensions in Annex 7 be sanctioned by the existing laws? Or does FIFA's power to apply regulations stem solely from the regulations and statutes it creates? If the latter is true, can meaningful legal oversight be applied at all? This is especially important given that FIFA had not consulted with the UAF or its clubs prior to issuing Annex 7. In other words, should FIFA in general be able to issue regulations for the stakeholders whose opinion and interests are neither heard nor considered? This could create a serious precedent granting too much power to an organization for which no meaningful alternatives exist. The issue is especially important given that the structure and powers of the other sports governing bodies often resemble those of FIFA.

Much can be said about the negative consequences of Annex 7 for the Ukrainian clubs. Clearly, the extraordinary circumstances in which the UAF-affiliated clubs found themselves, require actions of support to help football in Ukraine overcome the consequences of war. Stripping the clubs of their major assets – players - without due compensatory plan does more harm than good in this sense. It is logical then, that Annex 7 is being tested both legally and morally. While not challenging the decision to release players from contracts for their protection, the representative of Shakhtar Donetsk which continues battling Annex 7 in courts, claimed that the club seeks 'fairness and justice' with respect to all stakeholders when such decisions are made⁶. So far, however, FIFA has remained adamant to such requests.

⁶ T Panja (20 December, 2022) 'Fresh Off World Cup, FIFA Faces a Legal Challenge from Ukraine' The New York Times. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/12/20/sports/soccer/ukraine-fifa.html>